

FABRICATION AND AXIAL COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH CYLINDRICAL SHELLS WITH PYRAMIDAL LATTICE TRUSS

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ABSTRACT

We studied the mechanical response and failure of composite cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores under axial compression. We developed interlocking method and a hot press method to manufacture lightweight carbon fiber composite cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss constructions. For interlocking method, Firstly, longitudinal and transverse ribs will be mass produced by 7075 aluminum using wire cutting method. Both Longitudinal and transverse ribs will be assembled together to form core materials using interlocking method. Carbon fiber composite curved face sheets (170°) for both outer and inner skins of cylindrical shells will be made by hot press method in the curved steel mould. The outer skin of cylindrical shell will be assembled with curved aluminium pyramidal truss cores using J 242-A adhesive bonding, and then, the inner skin of shell will be built from two parts. For hot press method, Single walled cylindrical shells with pyramidal truss cores were made by hot press method firstly and then sandwich-walled cylindrical shells were fabricated by attaching inner carbon fiber-reinforced composite facesheets. In the analytical part of the study, The possible failure modes in axial compression of a composite cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores are illustrated in the following: (i) Euler buckling (EB), (ii) Overall buckling (OB), (iii) Local buckling between reinforcements (CB) and (iv) face crushing (CC). The collapse of the cylindrical shell is generally dictated by one of the competing mechanisms that depend on the geometry of the shell and the mechanical properties of the face and core materials. Four different failure modes were considered and theoretical models were presented to estimate the collapse strength associated with each failure mode. In the experimental part of the work, we used the analytical estimates to fabricate sandwich cylindrical shell that would allow probing the several different failure regimes. The measured collapse loads were in reasonable agreement with the analytical predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Weight reduction is an ever important design criterion for advanced aerospace structures resulting in steady incorporation of composites and cellular structures into aerospace systems. Cellular architecture in particular yields some well-known advantages over their traditional homogenous counterparts ranging from higher strength-weight ratio to exceptional buckling resistance in addition to effective energy absorption, shock mitigation, dynamic resistance and heat insulation. Strength-limited sandwich structures can be weight competitive with stiffener reinforced designs: the lowest weight designs in current usage [1]. Cylindrical Shells are a more likely candidate for sandwich construction than axially compressed panels or columns [2]. Considerable literature exists on the static strength of cylindrical shell subjected to in plane loading. In a range of load indices that are representative of most aerospace applications, the sandwich structures appear to be the most efficient [3]. Compared with foam core and honeycomb core, lattice truss core is the most weight efficient. Limited by manufacturing difficulties, researches of sandwich cylinders with truss cores are seldom reported.

In present paper, the details of fabricating the composite cylindrical shells with pyramidal truss cores are presented in Section 2. In Section 3, analytical models were developed for the crushing (i.e. axial compression) response of cylindrical shell. In Sections 4 and Section 5, the mechanical properties and failure modes were studied experimentally and compared to analytical predictions.

Conclusions are drawn in Section 6. More details about our work can be found in the published Journal paper [4, 5].

2 DESIGN AND FABRICATION

2.1 Interlocking method

Firstly, longitudinal and transverse ribs will be mass produced by 7075 aluminum using wire cutting method. Both Longitudinal and transverse ribs will be assembled together to form core materials using interlocking method (Fig.1a). Carbon fiber composite curved face sheets (170°) for both outer and inner skins of cylindrical shells will be made by hot press method in the curved steel mould. The outer skin of cylindrical shell will be assembled with curved aluminum pyramidal truss cores using J 242-A adhesive bonding, and then, the inner skin of shell will be built from two parts. Curved patch facesheet (10°) will be used to bond together with outer or inner skins in order to fill the gap between separate parts. Curved reinforcing facesheet (30°) will be bonding with curved patch face sheet in order to enhance the strength at the disconnected area. The manufacturing route for making the cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores was shown in figure 1(b).

Fig.1 (a) Sketch of the unit cell of pyramidal core. (b) Photograph of a carbon fiber composite pyramid lattice sandwich structure.

The critical parameters describing the geometry of the unit cell of curved pyramidal truss cores are sketched in figure 2. The relative density of curved pyramidal truss cores is given by:

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{\pi d h_1 (2R + 2h_c + 2t_f - h_1) + \pi d h_2 (2R + h_2 + 2t_f) + 120 d t_c (h_c - h_1 - h_2) \frac{1}{\sin \omega} + 30 d l_t (h_1 + h_2)}{\pi h_c (2R + h_c + 2t_f) l_t} \quad (1)$$

Fig.2 Unit cell of curved shell with pyramidal truss cores

2.2 Hot press method

Fig. 3 shows the fabrication process of carbon fiber composite sandwich cylindrical shell with low density pyramidal truss cores. The entire cylindrical shell including face sheets and truss cores

was made using carbon fiber based T700/epoxy resin prepregs (Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, China) via hot press.

The Carbon fiber composite unidirectional prepregs were cut into slender laps and put into grooves with the truss patterns. Both rib shaped moulds I and II are assembled together and only node surface area with carbon fiber prepregs indicated by red color in Fig.3 are exposed on the mould. The outer side of cylindrical mould were wrapped up with unidirectional composite prepregs along the transverse direction to form the outer face sheet perform. Outer semicircular steel moulds were enclosed to exert pressure on the surface of mould. All the parts of this mould shown in Fig.3 were made of stainless steel. Prior to processing, a release agent was brushed on the mold surfaces to allow easy separation of the structures from the mold after curing. We note that the mould described above can only be used to fabricate a cylindrical shell with single wall because the composite prepreg cannot be put on the inner side of the mould.

Fig.3 Fabrication process of carbon fiber composite cylindrical shell with low density pyramidal truss cores.

Composite curved face sheets using a hot press method in a curved steel mold. Three parts of inner skin for the cylindrical shell were bonded with inner side of curved pyramidal truss cores using J 242-A adhesive bonding and the inner skin of shell was built from three parts. These left gaps in the seams where the two face sheet meet, making inner face sheet vulnerable to premature failure. To remedy this situation, three parts of inner face sheet are connected with each other by bonding them at the same platform of curved pyramidal truss cores. It should be noted that both inner and outer face sheets are made by carbon fiber composite unidirectional prepregs with different fiber orientations due to differences in fabrication process. The moulds for both face sheets are different with each other, the outer face sheet was fabricated without gaps using a circular mould but the inner face sheet was made by three parts in the curved moulds. The outer and inner face sheets were made by unidirectional composite prepregs along the transverse and longitudinal direction, respectively.

The critical parameters describing the geometry of the unit cell of curved pyramidal truss cores are sketched in Fig. 4. The relative density of curved pyramidal truss cores can be shown to be:

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{8ldt + (a_1 + a_2)h_2b + 2(c_1 + c_2)h_1W}{2\pi h_c(2R + 2t_1 + h_c)W} n \quad (2)$$

Fig. 4 Unit cell of sandwich cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores

3 ANALYTICAL MODELS OF AXIAL-COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIORS

3.1 Structures made by interlocking method

The possible failure modes in axial compression of a composite cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores are illustrated in the following: (i) Euler buckling (EB), (ii) Overall buckling (OB), (iii) Local buckling between reinforcements (CB) and (iv) face crushing (CC). The collapse of the cylindrical shell is generally dictated by one of the competing mechanisms that depend on the geometry of the shell and the mechanical properties of the face and core materials. The analytical equations for above failure modes have been given in the following, respectively.

$$P_{EB} = \frac{k^2 \pi^2 (EI)_{eq}}{L^2} \quad (3)$$

$$P_{CS} = \pi(R^2 - r^2) \frac{E_{eq}(h_c + 2t_f)}{R} \quad (4)$$

$$P_{CB} = \frac{0.8\pi^3 E_f (2R + h_c) t_f^3}{3a^2} \quad (5)$$

$$P_{FC} = 2\pi(2R + h_c) t_f \sigma_f \quad (6)$$

3.2 Structures made by hot press method

The possible failure modes in axial compression of a carbon fiber sandwich cylindrical shell described here - (a) Euler buckling (EB), (b) Shell buckling (SB), (c) Local buckling between reinforcements (LB) and (d) face sheet crushing (FC).

$$P_{EB} = \frac{\pi}{2} (E_{f1} + E_{f2}) \frac{t_f}{h_c + 2t_f} R^4 \left\{ \left(\frac{R + 2t_f + h_c}{R} \right)^4 - 1 \right\} \frac{1}{L^2} \quad (7)$$

$$P_{SB} = \sigma_{SB} 2\pi R t_f = 1.2\pi (E_{f1} + E_{f2}) \frac{t_f}{h_c + 2t_f} \frac{(h_c + 2t_f)}{(R + h_c + 2t_f)} R t_f \quad (8)$$

$$P_{FC1} = [2\pi(R + t_f) + 20c_2] t_f \sigma_{f1} \quad \text{Inner face crushing} \quad (9)$$

$$P_{FC2} = 2\pi(R + h_c + 2t_f) t_f \sigma_{f2} \quad \text{Outer face crushing} \quad (10)$$

$$P_{FW} = \begin{cases} 2P_{FW1} + \frac{2\pi(R + 2t_f + h_c)}{2\pi(R + t_f) + 10c_1} P_{FW1} & (P_{FW1} \leq P_{FW2}) \\ 2P_{FW2} - \frac{2\pi(R + 2t_f + h_c)}{2\pi(R + t_f) + 10c_1} P_{FW2} & (P_{FW2} \leq P_{FW1}) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

4 AXIAL-COMPRESSIVE EXPERIMENTS

Static axial compressive tests were conducted on sandwich type shells with carbon fiber/epoxy facings and 7075 aluminum pyramidal truss cores using electro hydraulic servo system universal testing machine (100 ton). Experimental setup of lightweight cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores under axial compression was shown in Fig 5.

Fig.5 Sketch image of fixture on both ends of cylindrical shell and Sketch image of cylindrical shell under axial compression.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Interlocking method

Three configurations based on the cylindrical shell fabricated will be considered in our experiment. Specimen 1: shell with carbon fiber weave composites, Specimen 2: shell with four layers face sheet stacking sequence, $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$, and Specimen 3: shell with eight layers face sheet stacking sequence, $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_2$. Intercell buckling and face crushing have been investigated in our axial compression.

Fig.6 Mechanical behaviors of lightweight cylindrical shell. a) Specimen 1, b) Specimen 2, c) Specimen 3.

5.2 Hot press method

As the specimen was loaded in axial compression, no significant deviation from linear behavior is observed as shown in the global behavior till about 178kN. As the load reached near 178kN, the low intensity pinging noises which had started to emanate from the sample some time before, continued to increase appreciably till the load actually breached 178 kN .Thereafter, there was a sudden drop in load bearing capacity of the structure due to the onset of significant face sheet crushing. We note that the double face sheets of the sandwich structure restrain local buckling of ribs and failures are transferred to the face sheets, which results in enhancements in the load capacity. Fracturing occurred along fiber direction and craze penetrates throughout the cylindrical shell. The direction of craze in outer face sheet is almost horizontal but that of craze in inner face sheet is vertical due to differences in the fiber orientations.

Present sandwich cylindrical shell is assumed to have failed due to shell buckling but face crushing also occurred in the inner face sheet due to longitude left gaps crack between three parts of curved inner panels. The inner face sheet failure occurred firstly due to these left gaps between different curved face sheets and the experimental value is much smaller than analytical values due to these left gaps. The crack in the face sheet can have a significant influence on the behavior of thin-walled structures. The face wrinkling mode of failure was not observed in contrast to the previous study instead, face crushing being the dominant failure mode. The inner face sheet failed first and the craze fractured along the resin between unidirectional fibers, and then the outer face sheet also

fractured between unidirectional fibers. This behavior is further confirmed by the strain gage readings which show that the shell failed at the inner face sheet. The failure process of both face sheets are shown in fig 7(a) and (b). The fracturing cracks in both outer and inner face sheets have been sketched in Fig 7 (c) and (d), the failure occurred between unidirectional fibers.

Fig. 7 Failure modes of all composite sandwich cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores. (a) crushing of outer face sheet, (b) crushing of inner face sheet, schematic of the failure mechanism and fiber orientation of inner face sheet (c) and outer face sheet (d).

6 CONCLUSION

We studied the mechanical response and failure of composite cylindrical shell with pyramidal truss cores under axial compression. In the analytical part of the study, four different failure modes were considered and theoretical models were presented to estimate the collapse strength associated with each failure mode. In the experimental part of the work, we used the analytical estimates to fabricate sandwich cylindrical shell that would allow probing the several different failure regimes. The measured collapse loads were in reasonable agreement with the analytical predictions.

We fabricated and studied the mechanical response and failure of carbon fiber composite sandwich-walled cylindrical shells with low density pyramidal truss cores under uniaxial compression. The strain and failure mechanism were investigated in our experiments. We carried out both analytical calculations and direct experimental tests on the fabricated cylinders. Inner skin bears much more axial compressive load compared with outer skin because the stiffness of outer skin is much bigger than that

of inner skin. The inner face sheet failed firstly and the craze fractured along the resin between unidirectional fibers, and then the outer face sheet also fractured between unidirectional fibers. The specific strength of present all carbon fiber composite sandwich cylindrical shells with pyramidal truss cores is much superior to that of other cylindrical shells. Our results showed that all carbon fiber composite sandwich cylindrical shells with pyramidal truss cores could be used in the development of novel light weight multifunctional structures.

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